

HUMAN ACTION RECOGNITION FROM DEPTH MAPS AND POSTURES USING DEEP LEARNING

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ABSTRACT:

Human Activity Recognition is one of the active research areas in computer vision for various contexts like security surveillance, healthcare and human computer interaction. Over the past years, several methods published for human action recognition using RGB (red, green, and blue), depth, and skeleton datasets. Most of the methods introduced for action classification using skeleton datasets are constrained in some perspectives including features representation, complexity, and performance. However, there is still a challenging problem of providing an effective and efficient method for human action discrimination using a skeleton dataset. The first input is depth images and second input is a proposed moving joints descriptor (MJD) which represents the motion of body joints over time, in order to maximize feature extraction for accurate action classification, CNN channels are trained with different inputs and for Score fusion we are planning to use neural networks. Our proposed method was implementation on public datasets like MSRAction3D

INTRODUCTION

Human action recognition has been a popular research topic for a long time, not only because of their widespread application in a variety of applications, such as intelligent surveillance systems, human-robot interaction, and home care systems, but also because it remains a difficult research problem. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) have been widely used in many research areas, particularly computer vision and pattern recognition, thanks to the advancement of deep learning over the last few years, and have achieved remarkable performance on classification, detection, segmentation, and tracking tasks. In the subject of action recognition, there are a few things to keep in mind. As human-machine interaction becomes one of the most researched topics in multimedia processing, traditional communication techniques are being developed in order to address technological advancements and enable disabled people to communicate with machines and understand their activities using computer computing. Many research works have attempted to model and then recognise people's behavior using motion analysis. In this paper, we focus on human behaviour analysis from video scenes, and it

is worth noting that many information is hid behind gesture, rapid motion, and walking pace[1],[2].Due to the expressive features provided by the two types of data, recent human action recognition research has been directed toward using depth maps or body postures to represent the action[3]. A strong representation that gives distinct aspects of each action for classification is critical to the success of an action recognition algorithm. For some activities, using depth map data for action recognition is still confusing, resulting in incorrect classification because two actions may appear similar from the front, but they appear differently from the side[4].When substantial occlusions occur, the depth maps collected by the depth cameras are quite noisy, and the 3D positions of the tracked joints may be completely incorrect, increasing intraclass variances in the actions[5].They propose "Skepxels," a spatio-temporal format for skeletal sequences that uses CNN's 2D convolution kernels to fully leverage "local" connections between joints. They use Skepxels to convert skeleton movies into images with adjustable dimensions, and then use the generated images to build a CNN-based framework for successful human action recognition.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Zhao-Xuan Yang [7] Two single-view RGB datasets (KTH and TJU), two well-known depth datasets (MSR action 3-D and MSR daily activity 3-D), and one revolutionary multiview multimodal dataset are all used to validate the proposed methodology (MV-TJU). In both RGB and depth modalities, the extensive experimental data show that this method outperform the popular 2-D/3-D

component model-based approaches and other competitive techniques for numerous human action recognition. C. Krishna Mohan:[8] They proposed leveraging action bank features to recognise human actions in videos using a deep fully convolutional architecture. Action bank features are linear patterns that describe the resemblance of the video to the action bank films. They are computed against a predefined set of pictures defined as an action bank Miki, Hiroshi:[9] They offer a method for recognising objects that examines the relationship between human behaviour and object functions, with the goal of improving our method by adding human activities into dynamic object segmentation. Ziaeeferd, Maryam :[10] This research proposes a revolutionary normalized-polar histogram-based human action recognition algorithm. The action of accumulating skeletonized pictures was described.

As a motion pattern, it incorporates distance and angle. The most important aspect of this action is highlighted in cyan. It is represented by convolving all skeleton model frames round their centre. To categorize people's behavior, a multi-class SVM with two levels was utilised, first with generic features and subsequently with salient features. Mejdj DALLEL :[11] O"Industrial Human Action Recognition Dataset (InHARD)" is a large-scale RGB+Skeleton action recognition dataset that they introduced. Our database contains 4804 distinct action samples split over 38 movies from 14 different types of industrial activity. They complete the development of an end-to-end regression classification LSTM network in order to assess our dataset using the metrics

suggested. Yang Si :[12] They created a novel neural network by combining an autoencoder with a pattern recognition neural network. human activities deep neural network recognition. The model they suggested was confirmed by Experiments were conducted, and the model's benefits were discovered. by comparing performance They presented a model that was available. numerous significant contributions: They revealed a unique approach of combining multiframe data into a single picture in their study. This strategy is flexible. a method for mechanically extracting human action traits based on the deep neural network Lei Zong ,Chen Xu ,HongLin Yuan :[12] Currently, typical RF fingerprint recognition relies on a preset determination formula, which has drawbacks such as a high prior knowledge demand and a limited application range. They should employ an RF fingerprint identification method based on convolutional neural networks to tackle these issues (CNN). The study focuses on three aspects: RF fingerprint extraction, convolutional neural network architecture, and identification and verification of wireless transmitters. [13] fingerprint information is not utilised fraudulently. The deep convolutional neural network (DCNN) outperforms hand-crafted feature techniques. Most CNN models have the drawback of fixed scale images, however they have a new FLD method termed an improved DCNN with image scaling. For the first time, the confusion matrix is used as a performance indicator in FLD. The amounts of the experimental results based on the LivDet 2011 and LivDet 2013 data sets further confirm that our method outperforms others in terms of detection performance.

[14] To match latent fingerprints collected at crime scenes to a huge collection of reference prints and provide a candidate list of prospective mates, an automated latent fingerprint recognition system with high accuracy is required. They present an automated latent fingerprint recognition technique that uses Convolutional Neural Networks (ConvNets), and their results against a reference database of 100K rolled prints are 64.7 percent for the NIST SD27 and 75.3 percent for the WVU latent databases.

EXISTING SYSTEM:

Sometimes might be finding products is easy than waiting in the billing queue because it consumes more time of the customer. So now by taking the motivation of this scenario which was regularly done in all the Shoppe we are designing this system which can be benefited for the customer in all the means and also it was benefited for the Shoppe owner also. So, we design a system by this, the customer can know their bill while adding the items in the cart. The best and most useful example of this Supermarket Basket is that if a customer purchases can easily billed.

PROPOSED SYSTEM:

This system brings new innovation than existing shopping system. The main purpose of this project is to provide centralized and automated billing system using web. Along with the automatic billing some special features incorporated are along .We use new term that is Supermarket Basket

SYSTEM DESIGN

UML DIAGRAMS

UML stands for Unified Modeling Language. UML is a standardized general-purpose modeling language in the field of object-oriented software engineering. The standard is managed, and was created by, the Object Management Group.

The goal is for UML to become a common language for creating models of object oriented computer software. In its current form UML is comprised of two major components: a Meta-model and a notation. In the future, some form of method or process may also be added to; or associated with, UML.

The Unified Modeling Language is a standard language for specifying, Visualization, Constructing and documenting the artifacts of software system, as well as

for business modeling and other non-software systems.

The UML represents a collection of best engineering practices that have proven successful in the modeling of large and complex systems.

The UML is a very important part of developing objects oriented software and the software development process. The UML uses mostly graphical notations to express the design of software projects.

GOALS:

The Primary goals in the design of the UML are as follows:

1. Provide users a ready-to-use, expressive visual modeling Language so that they can develop and exchange meaningful models.
2. Provide extendibility and specialization mechanisms to extend the core concepts.

3. Be independent of particular programming languages and development process.
4. Provide a formal basis for understanding the modeling language.
5. Encourage the growth of OO tools market.
6. Support higher level development concepts such as collaborations, frameworks, patterns and components.
7. Integrate best practices.

system functions are performed for which actor. Roles of the actors in the system can be depicted.

USE CASE DIAGRAM:

A use case diagram in the Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a type of behavioral diagram defined by and created from a Use-case analysis. Its purpose is to present a graphical overview of the functionality provided by a system in terms of actors, their goals (represented as use cases), and any dependencies between those use cases. The main purpose of a use case diagram is to show what

CLASS DIAGRAM:

In software engineering, a class diagram in the Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a type of static structure diagram that describes the structure of a system by showing the system's classes, their attributes, operations (or methods), and the relationships among the classes. It explains which class contains information.

SEQUENCE DIAGRAM:

A sequence diagram in Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a kind of interaction diagram that shows how processes operate with one another and in what order. It is a construct of a Message Sequence Chart. Sequence diagrams are sometimes called event diagrams, event scenarios, and timing diagrams.

COLLEBORATION DIAGRAM:

IMPLEMENTATION:

MODULES:

- 1. Data Collection:** The first step is to collect multivariate time series data from the phone’s and the watch’s sensors. The sensors are sampled with a constant frequency of 30 Hz. After that, the sliding window approach is utilized for segmentation, where the time series is divided into subsequent windows of fixed duration without interwindow gaps (Banos et al., 2014). The sliding window approach does not require preprocessing of the time series, and is therefore ideally suited to real-time applications.
- 2. Preprocessing:** Filtering is performed afterwards to remove noisy values and outliers from the accelerometer time series data, so that it will be appropriate for the feature extraction stage. There are two basic types of filters that are usually used in this step: average filter (Sharma et al., 2008) or median filter (Thiemjarus, 2010). Since the type of noise dealt with here is similar to the salt and pepper noise found in images, that is, extreme acceleration values that occur in single snapshots scattered throughout the time

series. Therefore, a median filter of order 3 (window size) is applied to remove this kind of noise.

3. Feature Extraction: Here, each resulting segment will be summarized by a fixed number of features, i.e., one feature vector per segment. The used features are extracted from both time and frequency domains. Since, many activities have a repetitive nature, i.e., they consist of a set of movements that are done periodically like walking and running. This frequency of repetition, also known as dominant frequency, is a descriptive feature and thus, it has been taken into consideration.

4. Standardization: Since, the time domain features are measured in (m/s²), while the frequency ones in (Hz), therefore, all features should have the same scale for a fair comparison between them, as some classification algorithms use distance metrics. In this step, Z-Score standardization is used, which will transform the attributes to have zero mean and unit variance, and is defined as $x_{new} = (x - \mu) / \sigma$

where μ and σ are the attribute's mean and standard deviation respectively (Gyllensten, 2010).

CNNs has been proposed. Two action representations and three CNNs channels are used to maximize feature extraction. The posture data descriptor influence greatly on the whole recognition process by providing features to support the front view of the depth maps representation. Fusion operations between the output predictions of CNN channels are proposed to maximize the score of the right action. Since RGB-D datasets have a small number of training samples, two action representations are helpful to learn the model with a variety of feature and replace the lack of data. The results of our proposed method outperform most of the state-of-the-art methods on three public datasets. Although the proposed method showed high accuracy in action recognition and surpasses most of existing state-of-the-art methods, it was only evaluated using testing samples of humans performing actions in an environment with still cameras from a predefined distance. Future work concerns on collecting a dataset of depth maps and posture data of actions with a moving wearable camera or a robot to record actions performed spontaneously by humans from different views and distances [61], then we train the CNN model on the dataset samples and test the effectiveness of the proposed approach in real environment.

CONCLUSION

A method for human action recognition from depth maps and posture data using deep

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